

different temperatures. The ϕ° values thus obtained are given in Table 1, along with the corresponding values for other common salts reported earlier¹.

TABLE 1—LIMITING APPARENT MOLAL VOLUMES OF SOME COMMON SALTS IN DMSO AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Salts	ϕ° in ml mole ⁻¹ at					
	35°	40°	45°	50°	60°	70°
NaBr*	19.14	18.82	18.55	18.20	17.22	16.54
NaI*	35.65	35.42	34.92	34.40	33.72	33.15
NaNO ₃ *	27.94	—	27.70	27.30	25.76	23.85
KBr*	24.65	25.40	26.25	25.90	25.00	23.24
KI	40.99	41.54	41.44	40.74	39.79	38.73
KNO ₃ *	33.70	33.85	—	33.32	32.46	30.72
CaBr	30.52	31.09	31.57	30.92	29.82	28.13
CaI*	46.92	47.75	48.05	47.92	47.25	45.94
NH ₄ Br	34.10	34.25	33.75	33.30	32.70	31.65
NH ₄ I	50.55	50.15	49.50	48.80	47.95	46.80
NH ₄ NO ₃	42.80	43.00	42.90	42.50	41.80	40.10

*Values for these salts have been taken from our previous communication (1)

Additivity of limiting apparent molal volumes of salts in DMSO :

The additivity of ϕ° values given in table 1, has been tested in table 2.

TABLE 2—ADDITIVITY OF ϕ° OF SALTS IN DMSO AT 35°

(1) $X(\phi^{\circ}KX - \phi^{\circ}NaX)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	Selected values
Br ⁻	5.51
I ⁻	5.34
NO ₃ ⁻	5.76
(2) $X(\phi^{\circ}NH_4X - \phi^{\circ}NaX)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	
Br ⁻	14.96
I ⁻	14.90
NO ₃ ⁻	14.86
(3) $X(\phi^{\circ}NH_4X - \phi^{\circ}KX)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	
Br ⁻	9.45
I ⁻	9.56
NO ₃ ⁻	9.10
(4) $M(\phi^{\circ}MI - \phi^{\circ}MBr)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	
Na ⁺	16.51
K ⁺	16.34
Cs ⁺	16.40
NH ₄ ⁺	16.45
(5) $M(\phi^{\circ}MI - \phi^{\circ}MNO_3)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	
Na ⁺	7.71
K ⁺	7.29
NH ₄ ⁺	7.75
(6) $M(\phi^{\circ}MNO_3 - \phi^{\circ}MBr)/cm^3 \text{ mole}^{-1}$	
Na ⁺	8.80
K ⁺	9.05
NH ₄ ⁺	8.70

The almost constant values of the differences ($\phi^{\circ}_{AX} - \phi^{\circ}_{BX}$) for different anions (X = Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻) and that of ($\phi^{\circ}_{MX} - \phi^{\circ}_{MY}$) for different cations (M = Na⁺, K⁺, Cs,

NH₄⁺), indicates that the ϕ° values are additive in DMSO as in other solvents of high dielectric constant namely water², formamide³ and NMP⁴. This indicates that at infinite dilution the apparent ionic volume of each ion tends to a definite limiting value at a particular temperature, independent of the effect of opposite ions present in the solution. Thus we may write

$$\phi^{\circ}_{MX} = \phi^{\circ}_{M+} + \phi^{\circ}_{X-}$$

Thus the selected values of the difference in the limiting ionic volumes of two ions for different set of ions given in table 2 can be used to evaluate individual limiting ionic volumes for different ions, if the value for any one of these ions is known; although it is not possible at present. The attempts will be made to evaluate ϕ° (ion) in the next communication.

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Studies on the Binding of Hg(II) with Casein using Mercury Electrode.

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THE binding of metal ion with proteins has been studied by potentiometric¹⁻⁴, polarographic⁵⁻⁸ and equilibrium dialysis⁹⁻¹² methods. Similar studies with Hg(II) ions have not been reported so far. The later two methods could not be used due to some inherent experimental difficulties and, therefore first method was attempted for these determinations. This communication reports the result on Hg(II)-casein interaction by potentiometry using mercury electrode¹³. The results so obtained were compared with the pH metric method.

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Experimental

Reagents and Solutions :

Chemicals used were of A. R. grade and their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Fresh solution of 2% wholecasein¹⁴ (isolated from cow's skimmed milk) was prepared at pH 6.5 using doubly distilled water and KOH.

pH-measurements :

pH titrations were carried out on Beckmann Model G-pH meter in the same way as already reported by Randhawa and Malik¹⁵.

Potentiometric measurements :

Mercury electrode was prepared by forming silver amalgam on a silver wire. The following cell was set up.

Firstly the e.m.f. of cell containing varying amounts of HgCl₂ without protein at different pH values (5.5, 6.0, 6.5, 7.0) was measured on portable potentiometer for getting the calibration curves. Afterwards the e.m.f. of cell containing varying amounts of HgCl₂ and 2% casein was determined at the above pH values.

The potential measurement have a precision of 3% and pH data of 3.5%.

Results and Discussion

From pH measurements, the value of ν (the total number of hydrogen ions dissociated per 10⁵ gm of protein) was evaluated both in presence and absence of metal ion; using Tanford equations¹⁶ and the results are shown in figure 1. Hydrogen ion equilibria curves of Fig. 1 were used for computing number of hydrogen ions displaced by Hg²⁺ ions. This is equal to $\bar{V}_m$, the number of metal ions bound to 10⁵ gm of protein based Gurd and Murray's¹⁷ concept of one to one binding (one H⁺ for one Hg²⁺ ion). Upto pH 6,

Hg (II) ions compete with hydrogen ions and therefore, number of hydrogen ions displaced in this pH range would give the value of $\bar{V}_m$ for metal carboxyl interaction. Above the pH 6, carboxyl groups become deprotonated and Hg(II) enters in competition with hydrogen ions for imidazole groups. Therefore between pH 6.0 to 7.0 the excess of hydrogen ions displaced is a measure of number of Hg (I) ions bound to protein ($\bar{V}_m^-$) at imidazole sites, Interaction above pH 7.0 was not carried out to avoid the possibility of Hg²⁺ combining with OH ions and thus rendering the calculation of H⁺ ion dissociated difficult.

The intrinsic association constant for binding of Hg (II) ions with carboxyl and imidazole groups have been calculated by applying Scatchard's¹⁸ equation,

$$K = \frac{\bar{V}_m}{(n - \bar{V}_H - \bar{V}_m)C_F}$$

Where $\bar{V}_H$ and $\bar{V}_m$ are the active sites covered by hydrogen ions and metal ions respectively, n is the total number of intrinsically identical groups¹⁹, C_F is the concentration of free metal ions at equilibrium and K is the intrinsic association constant. The log K values for Hg(II) ions-carboxyl and imidazole are given in table-1. These values are quite close to the reported values²⁰.

TABLE 1—BINDING DATA CALCULATED FROM TITRATION CURVE (FIG. 1).

pH	H ⁺ dissociated in presence of metal ions.	H ⁺ dissociated in absence of metal ions.	$\bar{V}_m$	Free metal at equilibrium, (M/L × 10 ⁻⁴)	Log K
6.0	164	152	12	1.04	2.1227
7.0	183	168	15	0.80	2.4279

Potentiometric measurement

The e.m. f. values as function of HgCl₂ concentration with and without protein are plotted in Fig. 2. It is seen that the e.m.f. of cell containing protein is smaller than the e.m.f. of cell without protein showing thereby that some of Hg (II) has been bound to protein. The free HgCl₂ concentration has been determined from calibration curves (Fig. 2) at different pH values. It is observed that amount of Hg(II) bound increases with HgCl₂ concentration and reaches a saturation value. The maximum amount of Hg(II) bound increases with increase in pH. This is expected as the negative charges on protein increases with pH. It is further observed from table-2 that the amount of Hg(II) determined by Hg electrode is more than that obtained by pH metric method. This shows that Hg(II) gets bound to other sites where no hydrogen ions are displaced and hence this type of binding cannot be evaluated by pH-metric method.

FIG.1 Equilibrium between H⁺ and Casein.

FIG. 2.

TABLE 2—COMPARATIVE BINDING OF Hg(II) ON CASEIN, INITIAL CONCENTRATION OF Hg(II) = 2×10^{-8} M/litre.

pH	pH.—METRIC		POTENTIOMETRIC	
	Free metal at equilibrium (M/L $\times 10^{-8}$)	Metat bound (M/L $\times 10^{-8}$)	Free metal at equilibrium (M/L $\times 10^{-8}$)	Metat bound (M/L $\times 10^{-8}$)
3.5	1.20	0.8	1.15	0.85
6.0	1.04	0.96	0.9	1.1
6.5	0.88	1.12	0.6	1.4
7.0	0.80	1.2	0.55	1.45

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